

IN TECHNICAL EDUCATION , ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES OF LESSON BY BASING THEIR DESIGN

Olimjonova Gulnoza No'monjon's Daughter

a - second - year student of the "Foreign language and literature" department of
Gulistan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7676058>

Annotation

The future of our country relies on how effectively the education system is organized dependent process. The education system of every developing country development and leading to a new level of quality has been increased to the level of state policy. Looking at these factors, in our research work on the teaching of technical sciences are vital advanced methods are explored and about their usage of the feedback is provided.

Key words

Education; educational technology; innovation; interactive lessons; innovative approach; didactic game; technological map; information delivery methods; technological model.

Until today , in traditional education, students only access ready-made knowledge It was learned [1]. This method aids students to build up independent thinking [2], creative research, He took the initiative [3]. Modern pedagogical technologies are introduced classes. Students can google for the acquired knowledge by their own , independently It is aimed at them to learn and explore , and even make conclusions independently [4- 6]. During this process, the teacher is responsible for the process , formation, learning and improvement of the individual and the team creates conditions for education, and management, guidance functions [7-9]. In this learning process, the student plays the main role [10].

Pedagogue - scientists have been in the education system for years. Why do we teach? What Shall we teach? How do we teach? Additionally, looking for answers to their questions, how to effectively and the resulting Teaching is possible? They also searched for an answer to the question. This is a scientist and practitioners to the technologicalization of the educational process, that is to say , to the improvement of education to try to turn it into a technological process that gives a certain guaranteed result possible [11; 12], led to the idea that. The appearing of such an idea is the direction of a new pedagogical technology in the science of pedagogy brought about [12]. Today, in the educational process of educational institutions the main target is that grabbing attention is paid to the

usage of modern pedagogical technologies the reasons are: First, implementation of education that builds up personality in pedagogical technologies as far as possible. Law "On Education" and "National Personnel Training program" special attention is given to the implementation of developmental education [13- 15]

After what , pedagogical technologies are a systematic activity in the educational process creates an opportunity to commonly use the approach [16; 17]. Thirdly, pedagogical technology of the teacher education process begins with targets , to the introduction of a diagnostic system and managing the progress of this process b Encourages to design the technological chain in advance [18]. Fourth, pedagogical technology to utilize new devices and information methods due to the fact that their usage is depends on the requirements of the "National Personnel Training Program". ensures implementation [19; 20]. Pedagogical technologies in the educational process checks introduction of the teacher as the main organizer or consultant in this process causes it to function. This provides the learner more independence, creativity and willpower demands qualities. Gaining knowledge of pedagogical technology and their usage in education, experience ensures that students are knowledgeable and proficient. Innovation (English innovation) translates innovation. Innovative technologies are new introduction to the pedagogical process and the activities of teachers and students, Changes are introduced, and in its implementation mainly interactive methods are utilized. In interactive lessons, the role of the teacher is partly related to the activity of the students leads to Orientation to achieve. The key factor of these styles is that they are only It involves the joint together activity of the pedagogue and students. Such The process of pedagogical cooperation has its own characteristics, besides - The student should not be passive t during the lesson, think by their own , create and forced to find ; - Constant provision of students' interest in science during the educational process; - Students' attention in science are independently creatively applied to each issue approach reinforcement; - constant organization of cooperative activities of the pedagogue and students enters. Teaching special subjects by using new innovative technologies shows a good result [16]. That is to say , the learning process of students in these classes allocate by interactive games. As a consequence of this, the subject of the course is the student's It has been studied in the experiment that it can be gained for ages.

As a conclusion , using interactive methods and technologies creates more opportunities to students than an ordinary technical education and gives more

passion to lots of activities by their own . As a result, by learning and searching for new information, students will be able to gain more knowledge.

References:

1. Mamayunusova, M., & Ergasheva, Z. (2022). KIMYOVIY TEXNOLOGIYA FANINI O'QITISHDA DIDAKTIK O'YIN METODLARINING AHAMIYATI. Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 2(11), 707-711.
2. Шамшидинов, И. Т., Мирзакулов, Х. Ч., & Мамуров, Б. А. (2017). Переработка магнийсодержащих фосфоритов на экстракционную фосфорную кислоту. Universum: технические науки, (2 (35)), 84-89.
3. Hasanboyev, I., Abdusamatov, K., & Rivojiddinov, I. (2022). KITOVBXONLIK ISTIQBOLINING ASOSIY OMILLARI. Science and innovation, 1(B5), 560-563.
4. G'oyipov, A., Mamayunusova, M., & Ergasheva, Z. (2022). QOVOQ MAG 'ZINING TARKIBINI TADQIQ ETISH. Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot, 1(24), 596-599.
5. Мамуров, Б. А., & Шамшидинов, И. Т. (2021). Исследование процесса термообработки известняка для получения кальциймагнийсодержащих фосфорных удобрений. In Современные технологии и автоматизация в технике, управлении и образовании (pp. 101-104).
6. Мамуров, Б. А., & Шамшидинов, И. Т. (2020). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ДОЛОМИТА ПРИ ПОЛУЧЕНИИ ОДИНАРНЫХ ФОСФОРНЫХ УДОБРЕНИЙ. Символ науки, (9 22-24).
7. Shermatov, A., & Maulyanov, S. (2022). ЎСИМЛИК ТАРКИБИДАН КОЛХИЦИН ВА КОЛХАМИН АЛКАЛОИДЛАРИНИ АЖРАТИБ ОЛИШ КИНЕТИКАСИ. Science and innovation, 1(A5), 431-436.
8. Shamshidinov, I., Qodirova, G., Mamurov, B., Najmiddinov, R., & Nishonov, A. (2022). Экстракцион фосфат кислотани оҳактош хомашёси билан нейтраллаш асосида кальций ва магний фосфатли ўғитлар олиш. Science and innovation, 1(A4), 161-169.
9. Жураев, М. У., Каримов, А. М., & Ботиров, Э. Х. (2022). Scutellaria adenostegia Briq ўсимлиги таркибидаги апигенин (5, 7, 4'-тригидроксифлавоноид) ни ажратиб олиш ва таҳлил қилиш. Ta'lim fidoyilari, 22(7), 178-179.
10. Мамуров, Б. А., & Шамшидинов, И. Т. (2022). ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОЦЕССА ПОЛУЧЕНИЯ КАЛЬЦИЙ И МАГНИЙФОСФАТНЫХ УДОБРЕНИЙ ПУТЕМ НЕЙТРАЛИЗАЦИИ ЭКСТРАКЦИОННОЙ ФОСФОРНОЙ КИСЛОТЫ ДОЛОМИТОМ. Universum: технические науки, (7-3 (100)), 13-16.
11. Kodirova, G., Shamshidinov, I., Sulstonov, B., Najmiddinov, R., & Mamurov, B. (2021). Investigation of the Process of Purification of Wet-Process Phosphoric

Acid and Production of Concentrated Phosphoric Fertilizers Based on it. Chemical Science International Journal, 30(1).

12. Rakhmonov, D., & Gayipov, A. (2022). STUDY OF COMPOSITION AND CRITICAL PARAMETERS OF DUST FROM LOCAL COTTON INDUSTRY.

13. Dilshod, R., & Azizbek, G. (2022). STUDY OF COMPOSITION AND CRITICAL PARAMETERS OF DUST FROM LOCAL COTTON INDUSTRY. INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, 2(9), 77-81.

14. Ergashev, S., G'oyipov, A., & Alimuxamedov, M. (2022). KOMPOZITSION FENOL-FORMALDEGID OLIGOMERLARINING TARKIBINI NEFELOMETRIK USULDA O'RGANISH. Science and innovation, 1(A5), 424-430.

15. Mukhammadjon, J., Dilshod, R., & Botirov, E. (2022). ESSENTIAL OIL COMPOSITION OF TWO SPECIES OF SCUTELLARIA AERIAL PARTS FROM UZBEKISTAN AND THEIR ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITIES. BEST SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH, 1(1), 208-215.

16. Jo'rayev, M. (2022). KO'KAMARON O'SIMLIGINING KODENSIRLANGAN FENOLLI BIRIKMALARI. Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot, 1(23), 114-116.

17. Солиев, М. И., Атаханов, Ш. Н., & Акрамбоев, Р. А. (2015). Расчет электронных строений молекулы некоторых веществ с основе компьютерных программ. In НОВЫЕ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В НАУКЕ (pp. 12-15).

18. Дадамирзаев, М. Х. (2018). Микробиологические и физико-химические показатели полуфабрикатов овощных соусов. Universum: технические науки, (9 (54)), 24-26.

19. Пулатов, А. С., Сарibaева, Д. А., Ёкубжанова, Ё. Г., & Дадамирзаев, М. Х. (2014). Основное значение пива в системе рационального питания. Молодой ученый, (2), 184-186.

20. Atakhanov, S., Dadamirzaev, M., Akramboev, R., Otakhanov, S., & Dodayev, K. (2019). Research of physical and chemical indicators and food value of semi-finished products of sauce-past of fruits and vegetables. Химия и химическая технология, (3), 59-63.

